

ELIXIR Tools Platform 2024

Face-to-face Meeting Report

Tools Platform Leadership

Background

[The ELIXIR Tools Platform](#) helps communities find, register and benchmark software tools. These tools help researchers access, analyse and integrate biological data, and so drive scientific discovery across the life sciences.

The Platform plays a pivotal role in sustaining and advancing services that enable the findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability (FAIR) of computational tools, workflows, research software, machine learning models, and benchmarking resources. By supporting best practices, quality standards, and technical integration across the life sciences and beyond, the Platform underpins reproducible analytics, sustainable service delivery, and the professional development of software developers and users. In alignment with the [2024–2028 ELIXIR Scientific Programme](#), the 2024 hybrid meeting provided a strategic opportunity to review progress, address cross-Platform and project synergies, and plan the future development of the [Research Software Ecosystem \(RSEc\)](#) and related core services.

Event Format and Participation

The [2024 ELIXIR Tools Platform face-to-face meeting](#) was hosted by the University of Manchester, [ELIXIR-UK](#), and took place on 26–27 November in Manchester, UK, in a hybrid format with 21 onsite and 15 online participants, including work package (WP) leads, Node representatives, project partners, and ELIXIR Hub staff. The agenda combined plenary updates, structured WP discussions, interactive reflection sessions, and project engagement activities, fostering coordination with initiatives such as [EVERSE](#), [ELIXIR-STEERS](#), [EuroScienceGateway](#), and national projects. The meeting was co-chaired by members of the Tools Platform Executive Committee: Salvador Capella-Gutierrez (ELIXIR-ES), Björn Grüning (ELIXIR-DE), and Hervé Menager (ELIXIR-FR) with the support of the Hub Coordinator, Jonathan Tedds and Senior Science Officer, Mihail Anton.

Event Content

Day one focussed on progress and challenges across the WPs. WP2 presented the redesigned bio.tools interface and expanded metadata integration. WP3 reported on advances in software best practices, EDAM ontology updates, and quality indicators; WP4 shared developments in community benchmarking with OpenEBench and ARM-compatible Biocontainers; and WP5

outlined progress in WorkflowHub onboarding, environmental impact monitoring, and Pulsar network deployment. A reflection session identified strengths to maintain, areas for improvement, and new opportunities for engagement.

Day two concentrated on aligning Platform and project deliverables, integrating software quality indicators into the RSEc, supporting federated analytics, and mapping outputs to Science Tier proposals. Discussions also advanced sustainability planning for RSEc, including extension to other scientific domains and future Commissioned Services.

Outcomes and Conclusion

The meeting reinforced the ELIXIR Tools Platform's central role in enabling FAIR, reproducible, and sustainable life science analytics. Key outcomes included agreement on targeted community engagement, coordinated reporting across projects, and advancing RSEc as a cross-domain resource. Participants reaffirmed the Platform's commitment to collaboration with ELIXIR Platforms, Communities and Focus Groups, as well as international partners, including coordination with key externally funded projects referenced above involving Platform services.

Planning is underway for the 2025 and 2026 face-to-face meetings, to be linked with other ELIXIR Platform events to maximise synergies and participation and plan towards the future Work Programme.

Acknowledgements

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